

Distribution of the mound-building mouse on the territory of Košická kotlina basin (Slovakia)

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Abstract: In the lowland areas of the Košická kotlina basin (eastern Slovakia), the occurrence of the mound-building mouse, *Mus spicilegus*, was confirmed in 2002–2024. The occurrence was confirmed by typical autumn-winter mounds (n = 747) with food reserves consisting of weed seeds and grasses at thirteen localities. Long-term research confirmed that mice prefer mainly fallows, cereal and maize fields with grasses and weeds, which was also in agreement with literature data.

Keywords: mammals, *Mus spicilegus*, overwintering mounds, Rodentia

Introduction

The mound-building mouse is a small rodent living wild in a small spectrum of habitats outside human settlements (Macholán, 1999) where a group of several related individuals form autumn-winter mounds in which they store the seeds of weeds and crops and finally cover them with soil. Under the mounds, the mice also prepare underground nests with a system of burrows (Unterholzner & Willenig, 2000; Čanády et al., 2005, 2009; Hölzl et al., 2009, 2011a, b; Várfalvyová et al., 2010, 2011; Szenczi et al., 2011, 2012; Simeonovska-Nikolova et al., 2014; Csanády et al., 2019; etc.). Several functions of mounds were described, such as food storage, predator protection or thermoregulation (Szenczi et al., 2011, 2012).

In the southern regions of Slovakia, the occurrence of the species was confirmed based on the presence of typical mounds, where the species also reaches the northern limit of its distribution (Krištofik & Danko, 2003a, b; Mašán & Stanko, 2005; Čanády et al., 2005, 2009; Hölzl et al., 2009, 2011a, b; Várfalvyová et al., 2010, 2011; Sečanský & Fulín, 2013; Csanády et al., 2019).

Sokolov et al. (1990) showed, that the abundance of mounds in the same habitat can also vary

considerably depending on the number of weeds in each area. Frequent agrotechnical interventions aimed at weed control can significantly affect the total number of mice in a habitat type study. In general, ploughing in the autumn has a negative effect on the survival of the species' population (Muntyanu, 1990; Sokolov et al., 1990). According to Unterholzner & Willenig (2000), which studied the distribution of mounds in Austria and found that the frequency varies according to habitats. However, they confirmed that the occurrence of *M. spicilegus* in a particular habitat type was largely dependent on the presence of a wide range of grasses and weeds.

The current study provides information on the overwintering mounds and distribution in Košická kotlina basin (eastern Slovakia), which can contribute to the overall knowledge of the distribution in East Slovakia and of the ecology of this species.

Material and methods

As mentioned in the introduction, in 2002, the occurrence of the species *M. spicilegus* was confirmed in Slovakia based on typical mounds. Since then, long-term research and monitoring of the species (more than 20 years) in eastern Slovakia has been ongoing.

Fig. 1. Occurrence of *M. spicilegus* mounds in agrocenoses of the Košická kotlina basin. 1 – Kechnec, 2 – Belža, 3 – Bočiar, 4 – Sokoľany, site1, 5 – Sokoľany, site2, 6 – Haniska, site1, 7 – Haniska, site2, 8 – Valaliky, 9 – Košice city, part Šebastovce, 10 – Perín-Chým, 11 – Veľká Ida, 12 – Turňa and Bodvou, 13 – Žarnov. (A. Csanády).

In addition to repeated confirmation based on mounds (see Čanády et al., 2005, 2009; Csanády et al., 2019a), the species has also been monitored from an ecological perspective for a long time. Individuals were also captured to obtain morphological and reproductive characteristics (see Čanády et al., 2008; Čanády et al., 2014; Csanády et al., 2018, 2019b, 2020) as well as to obtain comprehensive knowledge about the epidemiological significance of this species (e.g., Čisláková et al., 2004; Danišová et al., 2015 etc.). At the same time, underground nests were also collected to obtain parasitofauna such as fleas, mites and ticks and other groups of invertebrates (e.g., Mašán & Stanko, 2005;

Várfalvyová et al., 2010, 2011; Šustek & Stanko, 2012).

The research was conducted the lowland areas of southeastern Slovakia in Košická kotlina basin at the following localities (Fig. 1):

1. Kechnec (48°33'19"N; 21°14'57"E, 202 m a.s.l.), on fields (76ha) about 0.5 km west of the village (currently on the territory of the Industrial Park Kechnec).

2. Belža (48°35'04"N; 21°15'54"E, 195 m a.s.l.), on field (8.4ha) about 0.5 km northwest of the village.

3. Bočiar (48°35'18"N; 21°14'05"E, 180 m a.s.l.), on field (6.0ha) about 0.3 km south of the village.

4. Sokolany, site1 (48°36'11"N; 21°13'41"E, 210 m a.s.l.), on field (9.3ha) about 0.3 km south of the village.

5. Sokolany, site2 (48°36'40"N; 21°14'47"E, 210 m a.s.l., in y. 2024): on field (12.5ha) about 0.8 km east of the village.

6. Haniska, site1 (48°37'17"N; 21°15'49"E, 197 m a.s.l.), on field (25ha) about 0.5 km northeast of the village.

7. Haniska, site2 (48°36'45"N; 21°16'01"E, 190 m a.s.l.), on field (7.8ha) about 1.1 km southeast of the village.

8. Valaliky (48°38'14"N; 21°16'06"E, 197 m a.s.l.), on field (20ha) about 1.7km west of the village.

9. Košice, part Šebastovce (48°39'14"N; 21°15'16"E, 214 m a.s.l.), on field (11.5ha) about 0.4 km west of the village.

10. Perin-Chým (48°32'08"N; 21°11'47"E, 200 m a.s.l.), on field (9.5ha) about 0.2 km east of the village.

11. Veľká Ida (48°36'54"N; 21°08'19"E, 241 m a.s.l.), on field (6.2ha) about 2.5 km northwest of the village, on the area of the Industrial Park Valaliky.

12. Turňa and Bodvou (48°36'03"N; 20°53'17"E, 185 m a.s.l.), on field (5.5ha) about 0.5 km east of the village.

13. Žarnov (48°34'45"N; 20°55'31"E, 210 m a.s.l.), on field (5.5ha) about 0.5 km south of the village.

Sites were checked annually (except for three years: 2008, 2018, 2022) in the autumn-winter period (August/September to December) using the "per pedes" method, with mounds found mainly in agrocenoses (such as fields with cereals, maize, sunflower, soybean or their stubbles) or fallow areas covered mainly with plant species of the genera *Chenopodium*, *Amaranthus* and *Setaria* (Fig. 2). The mounds were marked with a numerical code at each inspection to avoid repeated counting and overestimation of the total number. Below in part "Overview of mounds by dates and locations" are the recording dates with the number of mounds in the habitats, where (+) means that new mounds were recorded at the site compared to the previous date.

It should be noted that the research was carried out mainly in the vicinity of the village of Kechnec due to ongoing research related to the doctoral thesis of the author of this paper (A.Cs.). The other sites listed represented only supplementary and partial research, mainly related to mapping and measuring of

mounds. Moreover, after the first year of research, the main locality was seriously disturbed by the construction of the Industrial Park Kechnec, which did not allow long-term monitoring of changes in population abundance, and the research was focused primarily on the morphometric and parasitological-epidemiological aspects of the species.

Due to the great morphological similarity and sympatric occurrence with the house mouse (*Mus musculus* Linnaeus, 1758), the species was determined using somatic and cranial characters (see Čanády et al., 2008; Csanády et al., 2018). Species determination was also partially facilitated by trapping at the edge of autumn-winter mounds.

Results and discussion

Totally, 747 mounds were recorded for twenty-three years (2002–2024), with the amount varying between years and locations (Table 1). The marked differences in the number of mounds in different years at the same sites were partly a reflection of uneven search efforts (several personal reasons and caused by state restrictions during the duration of the COVID-19 pandemic). The second reason was that fields were often ploughed during their inspection. Long-term research confirmed that mice prefer mainly fallows, cereal and maize fields with grasses and weeds, which was also in agreement with literature data (Muntyanu, 1990; Sokolov et al., 1990; Unterholzner & Willenig, 2000; Krištofik & Danko, 2003a, b; Hölzl et al., 2009, 2011a, b; Szenczi et al., 2011, 2012; Simeonovska-Nikolova et al., 2014; Csanády et al., 2019).

Moreover, the significant decline in the number of mounds at the Kechnec site can also be attributed to the intensive construction of the Kechnec Industrial Park, which has been gradually taking place there since 2002. The same situation is currently also present at the Valaliky site (construction of the Valaliky Industrial Park – Volvo car factory is currently underway), where the areas with *M. spicilegus* mounds have been destroyed.

The first data on winter mounds of *M. spicilegus*, in which individuals accumulate various species of weeds and cereal spikelets as a winter stock, can be found in notes made by Petényi. He mentions the construction of mounds as a typical characteristic of the species (Chyzer, 1882). Below the above-ground part of the mounds, Petényi found nests made of plant

Fig. 2. *Mus spicilegus* mounds. A. Seed reservoir (without layer of earth) with *Setaria* spp. and *Chenopodium* spp. ears from Sokoľany, 2 October 2014. B. Seed reservoir (without layer of earth) with soybean ears from Belža, 2 October 2013. C. Complete mound (seeds with layer of earth) from Sokoľany, 2 October 2014. D. Mounds in autumn-winter season covered by snow from Sokoľany, 24 November 2024. (A. Csanády).

material of various sizes, ovoid or round, with an opening from the nest, which was orientated mostly towards to the west. According to Petényi, the mound-building mouse has therefore always lived outside of human dwellings and even wintered there.

Later, amongst the first important knowledge about the beginning and completion of the construction of the mounds, their dimensions, location and the size of nests, their burrow system and the plant composition of reservoirs, was that originating in Ukraine, acquired by Naumov, (1940) and Pisareva (1948). Sokolov et al. (1990) summarised older literature and presented new data from Ukraine and Moldova. Similarly, Zagorodnyuk & Berezovský (1994) and Kondratenko (1998) also mentioned the occurrence and above-ground dimensions of these mounds in Ukraine.

Mikeš (1971), in the years 1948–1964 in Vojvodina (former Yugoslavia, in today's Serbia), thoroughly researched not only selected aspects of the species ecology but also paid great attention to the structure of the winter reservoirs, the underground burrow systems and their nesting chambers.

Further data from Romania (Hamar, 1960), Austria (Festetics, 1961; Unterholzner & Willenig, 2000; Hölzl et al., 2009, 2011a, b), Moldova (Muntyanu, 1990; Simeonovska-Nikolova et al., 2014) and Hungary (Bihari, 2004, 2007; Szenczi et al., 2011, 2012) confirmed previous observations on the morphology of these autumn structures. Based on the presence of typical mounds, several authors confirmed the occurrence of the species in the southern regions of Slovakia, where the species also reaches the northern limit of its distribution (Krištofík

Table 1. The number of mounds observed in localities from Košická kotlina basin (eastern Slovakia).

locality	n	locality	n
Kechnec	275	Košice-Šebastovce	1
Belža	43	Perín-Chým	1
Bočiar	115	Veľká Ida	3
Sokolany	175	Turňa and Bodvou	1
Haniska	126	Žarnov	1
Valaliky	6	Total	747

& Danko, 2003a, b; Mašán & Stanko, 2005; Čanády et al., 2005, 2009; Hölzl et al., 2009, 2011a, b; Várfalvyová et al., 2010, 2011; Sečanský & Fulín, 2013; Csanády et al., 2019a).

Sokolov et al. (1990) emphasise that current agricultural conditions do not allow the stable settlement of the same habitats, as intensive crop harvesting and stubble cultivation force mice to migrate and concentrate in certain habitats. At the same time, there are currently very few natural steppes, and therefore the main places of survival are fields, but mainly their margins, unploughed areas, boundaries of windbreaks and hedgerows, as well as habitats around roads.

In general, ploughing in the autumn has a negative effect on the survival of the species' population (Muntyanu, 1990; Sokolov et al., 1990). Unterholzner & Willenig (2000) studied the distribution of mounds in Austria and found that the frequency varies according to habitats. However, they confirmed that the occurrence of *M. spicilegus* in a particular habitat type was largely dependent on the presence of a wide range of grasses and weeds. The opinion about greater preference in the settlement of sandy habitats was also controversial (Pisareva, 1948). Disagreement with this opinion was expressed by Sokolov et al. (1990), who believe that sands freeze deeper and, with the rapid warming that is common in Ukraine, water from snow would quickly seep through the soil. This would change the overall climatic conditions inside the mounds and nesting chambers, and soaking the food along with subsequently subcooling the individuals would cause increased mortality.

Despite differing views on the choice of habitats, all the above-mentioned studies confirmed that the

mounds were built, apart from crop fields, mainly on field and road margins and boundary strips of hedgerows and windbreaks, i.e., on uncultivated areas. All the mentioned occurrences sites of mounds were characterised by the presence of several species of weeds and grasses (*Setaria verticillate* (L.) P. Beauv., *Atriplex tatarica* L., *Amaranthus* spp., *Chenopodium* spp., etc.). These places represent deserted areas where mice survive, and where they are not exposed to intensive agricultural activities. Nevertheless, the mounds in these types of habitats were smaller than those in the fields. In addition, these habitats were also less suitable for their construction.

The autumn mounds inhabited by *M. spicilegus* are usually relatively large, in most cases oval and rarely conical in shape. The mounds represent an accumulation of seeds, ears of weeds and other plant parts covered with soil. Cultivated seeds (sunflower, corn, wheat) have been reported less frequently (Mikeš, 1971; Sokolov et al., 1990; Kondratenko, 1998; Csanády et al., 2019a). The beginning of construction was observed from mid-August to mid-November and peaked in mid to late September after forage ripening and at the end of the breeding season (Sokolov et al., 1990, 1998; Unterholzner & Willenig, 2000; Čanády et al., 2005, 2009; Csanády et al., 2019a).

In summary, there are still unanswered questions regarding changes in population size and the number of individuals involved in mound-building under natural conditions in Slovakia. Future field studies are needed to understand these issues. Furthermore, in some regions, this species is considered an agricultural pest, while in others, loss of grasslands and agricultural intensification may cause population

declines. Our findings could be relevant to various conservation and management actions.

Overview of mounds by dates and locations

Kechnec: y. 2002 (195 mounds): XI–XII.2002: a crop stubble, 120 mounds; a fallow, 75 mounds; y. 2003 (121 mounds): 13.XI.2003: a maize, 121 mounds; y. 2008 (4 mounds): 12.X.2008: a fallow, 4 mounds; y. 2004 (95 mounds): 20.IX.2004: a fallow, 1 mound; 11.X.2004: a fallow of drainage channel, (+15) mounds, a maize (+5) mounds; 19.X.2004: a maize, (+30) mounds; 25.X.2004: a maize, (+15) mounds; 29.X.2004: a maize, (+10) mounds; 02.XI.2004: a maize, (+4) mounds; 04.XI.2004: a maize, (+1) mound; 01.XII.2004: a maize, (+10) mounds; 07.XII.2004: a maize, (+5) mounds; y. 2005 (29 mounds): 30.VIII.2005: a crop stubble, 2 mounds; 12.IX.2005: a crop stubble, (+9) mounds; 14.IX.2005: a crop stubble, (+3) mounds; 05.X.2005: a crop stubble, (+15) mounds; y. 2006 (8 mounds): 08.XI.2006: a maize, 3 mounds; 09.XI.2006: a fallow area, (+5) mounds; y. 2007 (3 mounds): 01.IX.2009: a maize, 2 mounds; 08.IX.2007: a maize, (+1) mound; y. 2009 (9 mounds): 09.IX.2009: a fallow 4 mounds; 24.IX.2009: a fallow, (+1) mound; 03.XI.2009: a fallow, (+4) mounds; y. 2015 (6 mounds): 15.IX.2015: a soybean, 1 mound (Note: 20.X.2015 the soybean field was ploughed); 17.IX.2015: a maize, 2 mounds; 22.IX.2015: a maize, (+3) mounds.

Belža: y. 2004 (11 mounds): 25.X.2004: a fallow, 2 mounds; 29.X.2004: a fallow, 2 mounds; 02.XI.2004: a fallow, (+3) mounds; 04.XI.2004: a fallow, (+2) mounds; y. 2005 (15 mounds): 02.XI.2005: a maize, 10 mounds; a sunflower stubble, 5 mounds; y. 2010 (3 mounds): 14.X.2010: a crop stubble, 2 mounds, 28.X.2010: (+1) mound in crop stubble; y. 2011 (4 mounds): 15.XI.2011: a fallow, 4 mounds; y. 2012 (1 mound): 07.XI.2012: a maize stubble, 1 mound; y. 2013 (7 mounds): 02.X.2013: a soybean, 2 mounds; 08.X.2013: a soybean stubble, (+5) mounds; y. 2015 (2 mounds): 10.IX.2015: a soybean, (+4) mounds; 10.IX.2015: a soybean, (+4) mounds.

Bočiar: y. 2010 (7 mounds): 20.X.2010: a crop stubble, 4 mounds; 28.X.2010: a crop stubble, (+3) mounds; y. 2011 (11 mounds): 15.XI.2011: a crop stubble, 11 mounds; y. 2012 (30 mounds): 07.XI.2012: a crop stubble, 30 mounds; y. 2013 (4

mounds): 02.X.2013: a maize, 1 mound; a crop stubble, 3 mounds; y. 2014 (5 mounds): 02.X.2014: a potato field, 4 mound; a crop stubble, 1 mound; y. 2015 (5 mounds): 23.X.2015: a potato field, 5 mound; y. 2016 (8 mounds): 15.IX.2016: a potato field, 2 mounds; 20.X.2016: a potato field, (+5) mounds; a crop stubble, 1 mound; y. 2019 (7 mounds): 12.IX.2019: a fallow, 3 mounds; 22.IX.2019: a fallow, (+4) mounds; y. 2020 (22 mounds): 30.VIII.2020: a maize, 1 mound; 01.X.2020: a maize, (+4) mounds; 03.X.2020: a maize, (+5) mounds; 08.X.2020: a maize, (+2) mounds; 28.X.2020: a fallow, (+10) mounds; y. 2021 (11 mounds): 10.X.2021: a soybean, 7 mounds; 05.XI.2021: a maize, (+4) mounds; y. 2023 (5 mounds): 10.X.2023: a soybean, 5 mounds.

Sokoľany, site1: y. 2011 (35 mounds): 15.XI.2011: a maize stubble, 4 mounds; a crop stubble, 31 mounds; y. 2012 (15 mounds): 07.XI.2012: a crop stubble, 15 mounds; y. 2013 (8 mounds): 02.X.2013: a soybean, 8 mounds (Note: 08.X.2013: the soybean field was ploughed); y. 2014 (12 mounds): 02.X.2014: a maize, 2 mounds; a fallow, 4 mounds; a sunflower, 6 mounds; y. 2016 (3 mounds): 20.X.2016: a fallow, 3 mounds; y. 2019 (6 mounds): 12.IX.2019: a fallow, 6 mounds; y. 2024 (96 mounds): site1: 18.XI.2024: a fallow, 11 mounds (Note: 24.XI.2024: a fallow was ploughed); site2: 24.XI.2024: a maize stubble, 50 mounds (Note: 01.XII.2024: a maize stubble was ploughed); a fallow, 30 mounds (Note: 03.XII.2024: a maize stubble was ploughed).

Haniska, site1: y. 2004 (9 mounds): 10.XI.2004: a maize, 7 mounds; a soybean, 2 mounds; y. 2005 (8 mounds): 02.XI.2005: a maize, 5 mounds; a crop stubble, 3 mounds; y. 2010 (4 mounds): 20.X.2010: a crop stubble, 3 mounds; 28.X.2010: a crop stubble, (+1) mounds; y. 2011 (9 mounds): 15.XI.2011: a crop stubble, 9 mounds; y. 2012 (3 mounds): 07.XI.2012: a crop stubble, 3 mounds; y. 2014 (2 mounds): 02.X.2014: a crop stubble, 2 mounds; y. 2015 (3 mounds): 02.X.2014: a maize stubble, 3 mounds; y. 2016 (1 mound): 20.X.2016: a maize, 1 mound; y. 2017 (1 mound): 07.X.2017: a fallow, 1 mound; site2: y. 2020 (50 mounds): 15.XI.2020: a fallow, 50 mounds; y. 2021 (6 mounds): 31.X.2021: a maize, 1 mound; 01.XI.2021: a maize, (+1) mound; 05.XI.2021: a maize, (+2) mounds; 10.XI.2021: a maize, (+2) mounds; y. 2023 (8 mounds): 10.X.2023: a maize, 1 mound; 17.X.2023: a maize, (+4) mounds;

29.X.2023: a maize (+1) mound; a fallow (+2) mounds; y. 2024 (22 mounds): 18.XI.2024: a fallow, 2 mounds; a maize stubble, 20 mounds.

Valaliky: y. 2010 (5 mound): a crop stubble, 5 mounds; y. 2013 (1 mound): 02.X.2013: a maize, 1 mound.

Košice, part Šebastovce: y. 2013 (1 mound): 15.X.2013: a maize, 1 mound.

Veľká Ida: y. 2020 (3 mounds): 16.XI.2020: a maize stubble, 3 mounds.

Turňa and Bodvou: y. 2013 (1 mound): 14.X.2013: a crop stubble, 1 mound.

Žarnov: y. 2013 (1 mound): 14.X.2013: a maize, 1 mound.

Perín-Chým: y. 2013 (1 mound): 08.X.2013: a sunflower, 1 mound.

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References

- Bihari Z. 2004 A güzüeger magyarországi elterjedése és építő tevékenységének jellemzői. [The distribution and the characteristics of the construction activity of the mound-building mouse in Hungary]. *Vadbiológia* 10: 107–114.
- Bihari Z. 2007 Güzüeger. [Mound-building mouse]. pp. 195–196. In: Bihari Z., Gábor Cs., Miklós H. (eds) Magyarország Emlőseinek Atlasza. Kossuth Kiadó, Budapest, 360 pp.
- Csanády A., Mošanský L., Stanko M. 2018 Cranio-metric comparison and discrimination of two sibling species of the genus *Mus* (Mammalia, Rodentia) from Slovakia. *Folia Zoologica* 67 (3–4): 158–164.
<https://doi.org/10.25225/fozo.v67.i3-4.a2.2018>
- Csanády A., Stanko M., Mošanský L. 2019a Are there differences in the morphology of communal mounds of overwintering mound-building mice

(*Mus spicilegus* Petényi, 1882) in Slovakia? *Acta Zoologica Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae* 65 (2): 167–180.

<https://doi.org/10.17109/AZH.65.2.167.2019>

Csanády A., Stanko M., Mošanský L. 2019b Are differences in variation and allometry in testicular size of two sibling species of the genus *Mus* (Mammalia, Rodentia) caused by female promiscuity? *Mammal Research* 64 (1): 31–38.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13364-018-0393-x>

Csanády A., Stanko M., Mošanský L. 2020 First knowledge of spring-summer demographic structure and reproductive characteristics of *Mus spicilegus* from Slovakia. *Biologia* 75 (7): 927–933.

<https://doi.org/10.2478/s11756-019-00342-8>

Čanády A., Mošanský L., Stanko M. 2005 First knowledge about morphology of the mounds built by mound-building mouse (*Mus spicilegus* Petényi, 1882) in Eastern Slovakia. *Natura Carpatica* 46: 159–164.

Čanády A., Mošanský L., Stanko M. 2008 Porovnanie biometrických znakov dvoch sympatrických druhov rodu *Mus* – *Mus spicilegus* a *Mus musculus* z východného Slovenska. [Biometrical characteristics comparison of two sympatric species of the *Mus* genus – *Mus spicilegus* and *Mus musculus* from eastern Slovakia]. pp. 52–64. In: Adamec M., Urban P., Adamcová M. (eds) Výskum a ochrana cicavcov na Slovensku. VIII. Zborník príspevkov z konferencie (Zvolen), Štátna ochrana prírody Slovenskej republiky, Centrum ochrany prírody a krajiny, 12.-13.10.2007, Banská Bystrica.

Čanády A., Mošanský L., Stanko M. 2009 First knowledge of winter ecology of the mound-building mouse (*Mus spicilegus* Petényi, 1882) from Slovakia. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 61 (1): 79–86.

Čanády A., Mošanský L., Uličná L. 2014 Variability of skull and dental characteristics in *Mus spicilegus* from the northern border of its distributional range. *Biologia* 69 (10): 1425–1430.

<https://doi.org/10.2478/s11756-014-0442-0>

Čisláková L., Stanko M., Fričová J., Mošanský L., Trávníček M., Halanová M., Mardzinová S., Štefančíková A. 2004 Small mammals (Insectivora, Rodentia) as a potential source of chlamydial infection in East Slovakia. *Annals of*

- Agricultural and Environmental Medicine 11: 139–145.
- Danišová O., Valenčáková A., Stanko M., Luptáková L., Hasajová A. 2015 First report of *Enterocytozoon bieneusi* and *Encephalitozoon intestinalis* infection of wild mice in Slovakia. *Annals of Agricultural and Environmental Medicine* 22 (2): 250–251.
<https://doi.org/10.5604/12321966.1152075>
- Festetics A. 1961 Ährenmaushügel in Österreich. [Mound-building mouse mound in Austria]. *Zeitschrift für Säugertierkunde* 26: 112–125.
- Hamar M. 1960 Systematics, distribution and ecology of mound-building mouse (*Mus musculus spicilegus* Petényi, 1882) in Rumanien. *Revue de Biologie (Bucarest)* 5: 207–219.
- Hözl M., Hoi H., Darolová A., Krištofik J., Penna D.J. 2009 Why do the mounds of *Mus spicilegus* vary so much in size and composition? *Mammalian Biology* 74 (4): 308–314.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mambio.2009.02.004>
- Hözl M., Hoi H., Darolová A., Krištofik J. 2011a Insulation capacity of litter mounds built by *Mus spicilegus*: physical and thermal characteristics of building material and the role of mound size. *Ethology, Ecology and Evolution* 23 (1): 49–59.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03949370.2010.529827>
- Hözl M., Krištofik J., Darolová A., Hoi H. 2011b Food preferences and mound-building behaviour of the mound-building mice *Mus spicilegus*. *Naturwissenschaften* 98 (10): 863–870.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00114-011-0837-5>
- Chyzer K. 1882 Reliquiae Petényianae. [Peténian relics]. *Természetráji Füzetek* 5 (2–4): 91–146.
- Kondratenko A.V. 1998 The mound-building mouse, *Mus spicilegus* (Mammalia, Rodentia) in eastern regions of Ukraine. *Vestnik zoologii* 32 (5–6): 133–136. (In Russian)
- Krištofik J., Danko Š. 2003a First findings and evidences of steppe mouse (*Mus spicilegus* Petényi, 1882) in the Východoslovenská rovina plain and Košická kotlina basin. *Natura Carpatica* 44: 279–282.
- Krištofik J., Danko Š. 2003b Distribution of *Mus spicilegus* (Mammalia: Rodentia) in Slovakia. *Lynx (Praha)* n. s. 34: 55–60.
- Krištofik J., Stollmann A. 2012 Steppe mouse – *Mus spicilegus*. In: Krištofik J., Danko Š. (eds) *Mammals of Slovakia: distribution, bionomy and protection*. Veda – Slovak Academy of Sciences (SAS) Publishing House, Bratislava, 188–190.
- Macholán M. 1999 *Mus spicilegus* Petényi, 1882. In: Mitchell-Jones A.J., Amori G., Bogdanowicz W., Kryštufek B., Reijnders P.J.H., Spitzenberger F., Stubbe M., Thissen J.B.M., Vohralík V., Zima J. (eds) *The atlas of European mammals*. T&AD Poyser Ltd London. Academic Press London and San Diego, 288–289.
- Mašán P., Stanko M. 2005 Mesostigmatic mites (Acari) and fleas (Siphonaptera) associated with nests of mound-building mouse *Mus spicilegus* Petényi, 1882 (Mammalia, Rodentia). *Acta Parasitologica* 50 (3): 228–234.
- Mikeš M. 1971 Ekoloshka prouchavana na mishukhunkashu (*Mus musculus hortulanus* Nord.) u Vojvodini. [Ecological investigation on *Mus musculus hortulanus* Nordmann in Vojvodina]. *Matica srpska. Zbornik za prirodne nauke* 40: 52–129.
- Muntyanu A.I. 1990 Ecological features of an overwintering population of the hillock mouse (*M. hortulanus* Nordm.) in the south-west of the U.S.S.R. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 41 (1–3): 73–82.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-8312.1990.tb00822.x>
- Naumov N.P. 1940 Ekologija kurgančikovej myši *Mus musculus hortulanus* Nordm. [Ecology of the kurganchik mouse *Mus musculus hortulanus* Nordm.]. *Trudy Instituta evolyutsionnoi morfologii, Akademii Nauk SSSR* 3: 33–76. (In Russian)
- Pisareva N.A. 1948 K ekologii i sistematike kurgančikovej myši. [Ecology and systematics of mound-building mouse]. *Sbornik Rabot Biologicheskogo Faculteta. Moscow University*, 32: 68–71. (In Russian)
- Sečanský M., Fulín M. 2013 Steppe mouse (*Mus spicilegus*) at Drienovec (Košická kotlina basin). *Natura Carpatica* 54: 119–120.
- Simeonovska-Nikolova D., Beltcheva M., Larion A., Nistreanu V., Metcheva R. 2014 Variations in the mound size of mound-building mouse, *Mus spicilegus* between Bulgaria and Moldova. *Bulgarian Journal of Agricultural Science* 20 (1): 125–128.
- Sokolov V.E., Kotenkova E.V., Lyalyukhina S.I. 1990 Biology of house and mound-building mice. *Nauka, Moskva*, 207 pp. (In Russian)

- Szenczi P., Bánszegi O., Dúcs A., Gedeon C.I., Markó G., Németh I., Altbäcker V. 2011 Morphology and function of communal mounds of overwintering mound-building mice (*Mus spicilegus*). *Journal of Mammalogy* 92 (4): 852–860.
<https://doi.org/10.1644/10-MAMM-A-258.1>
- Szenczi P., Kopcsó D., Bánszegi O., Altbäcker V. 2012 The contribution of the vegetable material layer to the insulation capacities and water proofing of artificial *Mus spicilegus* mounds. *Mammalian Biology—Zeitschrift für Säugetierkunde* 77 (5): 327–331.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mambio.2012.03.003>
- Šustek Z., Stanko M. 2012 Beetles (Insecta: Coleoptera) in the nests of mound-building mouse *Mus spicilegus* in four orographic units in Slovakia. *Muzeul Olteniei Craiova. Oltenia. Studii și comunicări. Științele Naturii* 28 (1): 66–78.
- Unterholzner K., Willenig R. 2000 On the ecology, behavior and morphology of the mound-building mouse *Mus spicilegus* Petényi, 1882. *Biosystematics und Ecology Series*, Verlag Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, Wien 17: 1–88.
- Várfalvyová D., Miklisová D., Stanko M. 2010 Communities of mesostigmatid mites (Acari, Mesostigmata) in the nests of *Mus spicilegus* (Rodentia, Muridae) in Slovakia. *Folia Faunistica Slovaca* 15 (2): 13–18.
- Várfalvyová D., Stanko M., Miklisová D. 2011 Composition and seasonal changes of mesostigmatic mites (Acari) and fleas fauna (Siphonaptera) in the nests of *Mus spicilegus* (Mammalia: Rodentia). *Biologia* 66 (3): 528–534.
<https://doi.org/10.2478/s11756-011-0050-1>
- Zagorodniuk I.V., Berezovsky V.I. 1994 *Mus spicilegus* (Mammalia) in the fauna of Podolia and the northern border of its range in eastern Europe. *Zoologičeskij Žurnal* 73 (6): 110–119.
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